

Teaching Future Economists to Work with Vocabulary: Methods and Importance**Shamansurova Nodira Azimovna****ISFT, English teacher.****magazinapple@gmail.com****Abstract**

Mastering specialized terminology in economic education is crucial for developing the professional competencies of future specialists. This article analyzes methods for studying economic vocabulary, their effectiveness, and their application in the educational process. Moreover mastering economic vocabulary is essential for aspiring economists, as it enables them to comprehend and analyze complex economic concepts effectively. A robust understanding of economic terminology facilitates clear communication, critical thinking, and the ability to engage in professional discourse within the field. By building a strong economic lexicon, future economists can enhance their analytical skills and contribute meaningfully to discussions and research in the discipline.

Key words: gnoseological methods, Language for Specific Purposes, Venn diagrams, cognitive mapping, economic terminology.

Annotatsiya

Iqtisodiy ta'limda maxsuslashtirilgan terminologiyani o'zlashtirish bo'lajak mutaxassislarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Mazkur maqolada iqtisodiy lug'atni o'rganish usullari, ularning samaradorligi va ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishi tahlil qilinadi. Iqtisodiy lug'atni o'zlashtirish iqtisodchilar uchun muhim, chunki bu ularga murakkab iqtisodiy konsepsiyalarni samarali tushunish va tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Iqtisodiy terminologiyani chuqur o'zlashtirish aniq muloqot, tanqidiy fikrlash va sohadagi professional muloqotda ishtirok etish qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi. Kuchli iqtisodiy leksikonni shakllantirish orqali bo'lajak iqtisodchilar o'z tahlil ko'nikmalarini oshirib, faning muhokamalari va tadqiqotlariga mazmunli hissa qo'sha oladilar.

Kalit so'zlar: gnozeologik usullar, maxsus maqsadlar uchun til, Venn diagrammalari, kognitiv mapping, iqtisodiy terminologiya.

Аннотация

Освоение специализированной терминологии в экономическом образовании имеет важное значение для формирования профессиональных компетенций будущих специалистов. В данной статье анализируются методы изучения экономического словаря, их эффективность и применение в образовательном процессе. Освоение экономического словаря важно для будущих экономистов, поскольку это позволяет им эффективно понимать и анализировать сложные экономические концепции. Глубокое освоение экономической терминологии способствует точному общению, критическому мышлению и участию в профессиональном общении в данной области. Формируя сильный экономический лексикон, будущие экономисты могут улучшить свои аналитические навыки и внести значимый вклад в обсуждения и исследования в этой дисциплине.

Ключевые слова: гносеологические методы, язык для специальных целей, диаграммы Венна, когнитивное картирование, экономическая терминология.

Economics, as a social science, stands out as one of the most captivating and frequently debated disciplines globally, which contributes to its popularity among our summer course offerings. For those aiming to deepen their understanding -whether to pursue advanced studies at A-Level or university, or simply out of personal interest - it's essential to become familiar with the fundamental concepts and terminology of the field. However, the vast array of economic terms can be challenging to master. Originating in the late 18th century, economics has evolved rapidly, embedding its vocabulary and ideas into everyday language. To assist learners in building a solid foundation, we've curated a list of essential economic terms with definitions. Reviewing these will provide a valuable starting point for further exploration and learning.

Mastering economic vocabulary provides students with the following opportunities:

- Accurately understanding and analyzing economic processes;

- Expressing clear and precise thoughts in scientific and practical activities;
- Effectively participating in professional communication.
- Methods for Working with Vocabulary

Reading and Analyzing Economic Literature: Regularly reading books, articles, and research related to economic sciences helps familiarize students with specialized terms and concepts, thereby enriching their vocabulary. Bilingual dictionaries are essential resources for mastering economic terms. For example, the “Concise Russian-Uzbek Economic Terms Dictionary” aids in learning economic terminology in both Russian and Uzbek. Courses and seminars dedicated to economic terminology are effective in expanding vocabulary. By attending these events, students can delve deeper into industry-specific terms. Completing Practical Exercises and Assignments: Writing essays on economic topics, preparing presentations, and engaging in discussions with professionals can enhance vocabulary. These methods develop students' practical skills. Online dictionaries and databases related to economic terminology are useful for expanding vocabulary. For instance, accessing available economic term dictionaries and databases on the internet can be beneficial.

In non-linguistic universities, students are increasingly engaging in extensive English courses. However, within Language for Specific Purposes (LSP) instruction, methodologies aimed at developing proficiency in specialized terminology remain underdeveloped. Given that terminology constitutes the foundation of professional language - encompassing its essential attributes and characteristics - it represents the most dynamic segment of vocabulary, continually evolving and expanding. This dynamic nature necessitates a systematic approach to addressing related methodological challenges. To effectively achieve educational objectives, foreign language instructors must comprehend the unique aspects of terminology, instructional strategies, and the individual characteristics of their students.

While LSP teaching incorporates various methodologies, the communicative, cognitive, and definitional approaches are among the most prevalent. This article outlines the stages of vocabulary introduction in the classroom and examines the teaching methods applicable at each phase. The analysis focuses on:

- The communicative method, which introduces economic vocabulary to students.
- The cognitive (or gnoseological) method, emphasizing the interplay between words and concepts, language and thought, and the linguistic and extralinguistic factors influencing terminology development and the semantics of individual terms.
- The definitional method, which involves analyzing meanings and identifying equivalents in the target language.

During initial professional communication stages, students are introduced to terms related to the lesson's topic. Subsequently, definitions are analyzed, and Anglo-Russian equivalents are identified. After memorizing these terms, students apply them in real communication scenarios. The communicative approach fosters monologic and dialogic speech skills, ensuring the appropriate contextual use of terms. Additionally, the study explores conceptual, semantic, network, and mental maps, as well as denotative text maps and Venn diagrams. These cognitive mapping techniques enable a reevaluation of central concepts by connecting them to students' experiences. Semantic maps, in particular, illustrate the lexical features of specific concepts and serve as effective tools for expanding foreign language vocabulary. Utilizing semantic maps helps establish mental associations between terms and their underlying concepts, allowing students to understand the interconnectedness of words rather than learning them in isolation. This structured knowledge, supported by visual aids, enhances the assimilation of new foreign language terminology.

Incorporating specialized vocabulary into economics education is crucial for students to effectively understand and communicate complex economic concepts. Mastery of this terminology enhances comprehension, facilitates precise analysis, and enables clear articulation of ideas.

A robust grasp of economic terminology allows students to interpret and analyze economic theories and data accurately. Familiarity with terms such as “marginal utility,” “opportunity cost,” and “elasticity” enables learners to engage deeply with economic texts and discussions. This foundational knowledge is essential for critical thinking and problem-solving in economics. Proficiency in specialized vocabulary empowers students to articulate

economic concepts clearly and persuasively. Whether drafting research papers, delivering presentations, or participating in debates, the ability to use precise terminology ensures that ideas are conveyed accurately and professionally. This skill is vital for future economists who must communicate complex information to diverse audiences.

Conclusion

Teaching future economists to work with vocabulary is essential for their success in professional activities. By employing the methods mentioned above, students can enrich their vocabulary and develop the skills to use industry-specific terms correctly and effectively.

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